

Eurodoc endorses the Open Letter: European Research and Higher Education Organisations Call On Commission Not to Neglect Their Needs in Lawmaking

Science Europe, together with the European University Association (EUA), The Guild of European Research-Intensive Universities, the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA), Knowledge Rights 21 (KR21), LIBER (Ligue des Bibliothèques Européennes de Recherche – Association of European Research Libraries), SPARC Europe, and Stichting eIFL.net (EIFL) have issued an open letter on January 31st, 2024.¹ In their letter, the signatories address Secretary-General of the European Commission, urging for stronger efforts to integrate the needs and concerns of the research and education sectors into the Commission's guidance on the better regulation agenda.²

The Better Regulation agenda aims to

- Ensure EU policy making is based on evidence
- Making EU laws simpler and better, and avoiding unnecessary burdens
- Involving citizens, businesses and stakeholders in the decision-making process

However, the signatories of the Open Letter identify a number of recent EU policies that in different ways fell short of the needs of the two academic sectors, for example with regards to the digital services act.

In particular, the Open Letter calls for the following five actions:

1. *Review the European Union's Innovation Principle³ to ensure it reflects the importance of public sector research and education.*

As stated on the Commission's website, the Innovation Principle is a tool to help achieve EU policy objectives by ensuring that legislation is designed in a way that creates the best possible conditions for innovation to flourish. It is a very worthwhile approach to go about this holistically, by dividing it into the three phases of agenda-setting, legislating and implementing, which are intended as a continuous cycle. Tying it so strongly to innovators and economic actors implies an exclusivity that in the long run will certainly be detrimental, so in this we agree with the notion of ScienceEurope et al. to ensure the proper inclusion and reflection of both the public research sector and the public education sector.

Furthermore, beyond the phrasing by Science Europe et al., we want to highlight the role of individual researchers and educators. They are key stakeholders shaping the future society and economy, and they are strongly impacted by the legislation as well, so it is crucial to include representatives of individuals at the same level as representatives of the institutions.

¹ <https://www.scienceeurope.org/media/dthffrsx/press-release-open-letter-on-research-and-higher-education-in-ec-impact-assessments.pdf>

² https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-making-process/planning-and-proposing-law/better-regulation_en

³ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/law-and-regulations/ensuring-eu-legislation-supports-innovation_en#what-is-the-innovation-principle

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- 2. Update the Commission's Better Regulation Toolkit⁴ and any other guidance for impact assessment to properly and fully include the needs and interests of higher education and research as well as ensure the protection of academic freedom. Furthermore, there should be a regular evaluation whether this has happened.*

We fully agree with the assessment of Science Europe et al. in that the toolkit provided should not lead to contradictory conclusions, but that it needs to support the practical implementation of academic freedom as the right of the individual academic as well as the responsible implementation and assurance of institutional autonomy. As indicated in the policy-making cycle, this further requires continuous monitoring and, if indicated, actions to improve on any shortcomings.

- 3. Ensure – as a matter of internal procedure – that the impacts on education and research in any legislation are duly considered and improved through inter-service collaboration. In particular, those related to intellectual property law and to the Digital Agenda need immediate attention.*

The inter-service collaboration and the statistical evidence on impacts, both regarding education and research, are important factors to be ensured. Again, these need to be aligned with evidence from institutional representatives as well as from representatives of individual researchers and educators, to achieve a balanced input and a meaningful policy as the outcome of the process.

- 4. Actively reach out to education and research groups and institutions as part of the impact assessment process in order to receive informed views and opinions on the impact on the sector.*

The straightforward approach of statistical analysis via the national statistical agencies has shown shortcomings in the past, indicating a strong need to be complemented by inputs of relevant stakeholder groups. With regards to the research sector and the higher education sector, this requires views, opinions and analyses by both institutions and respective individuals to be taken into account through the corresponding stakeholder groups and their representatives.

- 5. Act now to remedy the negative impacts of recent digital legislation on the research sector.*

The digital sphere is gaining ever more importance and the digital legislation indeed requires a better focus to foster the sustainable development of the corresponding platforms, tools and competences. Given the high impact on society and economy already today and the prospective roles that are predictable with a high certainty, it will be crucial to provide the best possible policy framework to ensure a resilient society and a competitive economy even in the near future. Both of these are substantially coined by the public

⁴ https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-making-process/planning-and-proposing-law/better-regulation/better-regulation-guidelines-and-toolbox_en

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research and education sectors, which needs to be properly represented in the updated legislation.

Therefore, Eurodoc endorses the Open Letter and joins into the call to action for the European Commission, with particular respect to the needs of the individuals in research and education, as highlighted in the explanations above.

The statement was authored by the administrative board of Eurodoc 2023/2024

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